

High-sensitive Intensity Modulated Curvature Sensor Based on D-shaped Fiber Wrapped in PDMS Film

Fei Li¹, Yaqi Wen¹, Kai Wan¹, Fanbu Feng¹, Bing Sun^{1,2,*}, Kaiming Zhou²

¹College of Electronics and Optical Engineering, Nanjing University of Posts and Telecommunications, Nanjing 210023, China

²Aston Institute of Photonic Technologies, Aston University, Birmingham B4 7ET, UK

*b.sun@njupt.edu.cn

Abstract: The curvature sensor, which consists of wrapping the coreless D-shaped optical fiber in polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) film is experimentally proposed. High-sensitive curvature measurements are achieved with sensitivities of 2.04 dB/m^{-1} and 2.66 dB/m^{-1} in the X+ and X- direction, respectively. Moreover, the proposed sensor demonstrates a low temperature dependence of $0.025 \text{ dB}^\circ\text{C}$.

1. Introduction

The curvature measurements play an important role in the fields of aerospace, geophysics, mechanical engineering, robotic arms, and structural health monitoring [1-2]. Compared with electrical sensors, optical fiber sensors are widely researched as they possess inherent advantages, such as relative ease of handling, small footprint, high sensitivity, ability for multiplexed configurations, and immune to electromagnetic fields. Several schemes of fiber-optic curvature sensors (FOCSs) based on the fiber gratings [3-4], the single-mode-multimode-single-mode fiber structures [5], and interferometric structures [6-7] have been demonstrated. However, some issues are emerging such as the time-consuming direction alignment of curvature measurement, small detection range, wavelength demodulation with high cost.

In recent years, D-shaped optical fibers have been employed to fabricate various sensors [8-9]. Here we take advantage of coreless D-shaped single-mode fiber structure to implement a high-sensitive curvature sensor, where the whole sensing section is embedded in the polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) film with thicknesses of hundreds of micros. The PDMS film can show excellent flexibilities to solve the extreme fragility of the bare D-shaped optical fibers. Furthermore, the panel ($40 \times 15 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}$) would be suitable for the direction alignment of bending measurement. For instance, the curvature sensor demonstrates sensitivities of 2.66 dB/m^{-1} and -2.39 dB/m^{-1} , respectively, with two bending directions (+Y and -Y) in the curvature range from 0 to 3.03 m^{-1} .

2. Theoretical Principle

Fig. 1 (a) The schematics of the three-dimensional structure of the curvature sensor. (b) The xz-plane of the coreless D-shaped fiber.

Fig. 1 (a) shows the schematics of the three-dimensional structure of the curvature sensor, which consists of the coreless D-shaped SMF and the PDMS panel. The main sensing section includes three parts of transitional region 1 ($Lt 1$), coreless flat region and transitional region 2 ($Lt 2$). The length (Lf) and the residual thickness (RT) of the core flat section could be controlled by using home-made polishing system. In special, the coreless flat section

works as a D-shaped multimode waveguide and the curve polished surface could efficiently excite the cladding modes to contribute to the multimode interference [10]. The operation involved in the proposed scheme can be described by means of the modal interference theory and expressed as

$$I = I_{clad,j} + I_{clad,k} + 2\sqrt{I_{clad,j}I_{clad,k}} \cos \Phi \quad (1)$$

where $I_{clad,j}$ and $I_{clad,k}$ are the intensities of the dominant modes, i.e., the j -th and k -th cladding modes, respectively. And the phase difference can be considered through the differential modal group index [11] as

$$\Phi \approx \Phi_0 - \frac{2\pi\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0^2} \Delta m_{eff} L, \text{ with } \Delta m_{eff} = \Delta n_{eff} - \lambda_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \Delta n_{eff} \quad (2)$$

where the deviation from the center wavelength λ_0 is $\Delta\lambda = \lambda - \lambda_0$, the effective index difference is defined as $\Delta n_{eff} = n_{eff}^{clad,j} - n_{eff}^{clad,k}$. As a result, the output light intensity presents minimums in the spectrum.

On the other hand, the sensing section was fixed between two fiber holders among which a fiber holder could be moved longitudinally. The bent fiber was normally approximated as an arc of circle. So the sensor's curvature was given by

$$C = 1/R = 2h / (h^2 + d^2) \quad (3)$$

where R is the curvature radius, h is the bending displacement, and d is the half distance between the edges of the two clamps. Our previous research [12] implies that the stress concentrations are induced when a given curvature is applied. Note that there is no stress concentration existed in the two clamps.

3. Experimental Fabrication and Results

Fig. 2(a) Comparison of transmission spectrums between the D-shaped fiber wrapped and unwrapped PDMS. (b) Schematic diagram of curvature detection system.

We take advantage of the home-developed fiber polishing system to obtain the coreless D-shaped fibers with controllable residual thickness (RT) and length (L). During the polishing process, the side view of the polished fiber was monitored by use of a microscope, and the residual thickness (RT) of the D-shaped fiber was measured along the whole polished region. Thus, a thin PDMS film has been immobilized on the flat surface of the coreless D-shaped fiber by the dip coating method, and then the whole fiber structure is rapidly solidified by means of placing it at 80 °C for 4 hours. It should be noted that the PDMS solution is prepared by means of mixing two precursors of silicone elastomer and curing agent with a 10:1 ratio, then leave it in a vacuum for 10 minutes to remove the bubbles. As a result of optimizing the dipping condition, i.e., the speed and the dipping time, the D-shaped fibers can be encapsulated in the well-designed PDMS film with thickness of hundreds of microns. Note that a certain amount of flexibility is built into the curvature measurements with the help of the PDMS panel. Fig. 2(a) shows the comparison of transmission spectra between PDMS wrapped and unwrapped D-shaped fiber, while the RT of $\sim 43 \mu\text{m}$ and the length L (consisting of the length of L_1 , L_f and L_2) of $\sim 5 \text{ mm}$ is characterized. The experimental setup including a home-made curvature-changing system, an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA, AQ6317C, with a resolution of 0.02 nm), a broadband source (ASE, with a spectral range of 1250 ~ 1650 nm), and a high precision displacement platform has been shown in Fig. 2(b). Note that owing to the PDMS film (a refractive index of 1.4204), the transmission has a redshift.

Fig.3 (a) Spectral responses of the sensor for different curvature in the X+ direction. (b) The corresponding dip intensity.

The measured transmission spectra shift of the PDMS wrapped D-shaped fiber under different curvatures was shown in Fig. 3(a). It could be seen that the intensity of the dip, i.e., dip I, is increased with the curvature (X+ direction) while the relationship between curvature and intensities of dip I in the spectrum was plotted in Fig. 3(b). A linear response is obtained with a high sensitivity of 2.04 dB/m⁻¹. Moreover, the wavelength of the dip has a little change with the bending of the sensing section. On the other hand, transmission spectra vs the curvatures (X- direction) have also been concluded in Fig. 4(a). It can be clearly observed that the intensity of the dip is decreased with the curvature while the corresponding sensitivity is 2.66 dB/m⁻¹, as shown in Fig. 4(b). Note that the curvature measurements during X+ and X- direction can induce stretch and squeeze to the PDMS film. Thus, the asymmetrical encapsulation of the D-shaped fiber in the PDMS film may contribute to the difference of the sensitivity in the curvature measurements.

Fig.4 (a) Spectral responses of the sensor for different curvature in the X- direction. (b) The corresponding dip intensity.

Furthermore, the temperature response of the curvature sensor is also investigated by means of placing it into a column oven (LCO 102 DOUBLE) with a temperature range from room temperature to 80 °C. In addition, a differential thermocouple (UNI-T UT320) is used to measure the temperature with an accuracy of 0.1 °C. It should be noted that the temperature in the oven rose gradually from 25 to 80 °C with a step of 10 °C, and then maintained about 20 min during each temperature rise. As shown in Fig. 5, the dip intensity induced by temperature is about 1.375 dB from 25 to 80 °C, i.e., a sensitivity of 0.025 dB/°C. As a result, there is nearly no variation in dip intensity been measured. It would provide a new way for high-sensitive detection of curvature change in the temperature cross-interference issue.

Fig. 5 The dip intensity of the sensor versus temperature at dip I, the curvature responses are also shown for comparison.

4. Conclusion

In summary, a temperature-insensitive and high-sensitive curvature sensor based on D-shaped fiber wrapped in the PDMS film is experimentally proposed with X+ and X- direction in the range from 0 to 3.03 m⁻¹. It's believed that it would find potential applications in severe environment.

5. References

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